

Methods: Data from a pair of 3 Tesla scanners – a MR-750 (Discovery) model scanner running software version DV26.0_R03 from General Electric (GE), and a Skyra model scanner running software version VE11C from Siemens – were used for this work.

Acquisition: On the Siemens platform, data were acquired using the vendor’s 32-channel head coil. The pulse sequence used, based on the vendor’s product EPI sequence, was enhanced to collect multi-echo EPI data, but was otherwise unmodified. Data were acquired from a FBIRN phantom using the following pulse sequence parameters: field of view (FOV) = 216mm, image matrix = 72 x 72, slice thickness = 3 mm, TR = 2000 ms, TE = 27 ms, with no accelerated or partial *k*-space options utilized, with 5 repetitions of 37 slices each prescribed for this acquisition.

On the GE platform, data were acquired using the vendor’s 8-channel head coil. The pulse sequence utilized on this platform, also based on this vendor’s product EPI sequence, was enhanced to collect multi-echo data and allow more flexible image matrix and acceleration options. Enhancements were made to store the ramp-sampled EPI trajectory timing information into the vendor-generated raw data file. Data from this scanner were acquired using another FBIRN phantom (i.e. different from the one used on the Siemens scanner) with the following parameters: FOV = 240 mm, image matrix = 96 x 96, slice thickness = 2.5 mm, TR = 2000, TE = 31 ms, again with no accelerated or partial *k*-space options utilized, and 7 repetitions of 23 slices each prescribed for this acquisition.

Processing: Acquired raw (*k*-space) data in vendors’ proprietary formats were converted into the ISMRMRD format using the corresponding software, obtainable at: <https://github.com/ismrmrd>. The converted data were processed in a Jupyter notebook [<https://jupyter.org/>] (accessible at the link specified in the **Resources** section below) running Python [<https://www.python.org/>], utilizing Numpy and the ISMRMRD Python support modules. Beside extracting the data from an ISMRMRD formatted raw data file, and organizing the data depending on its labeling, the notebook also contains algorithms to perform Nyquist ghost [5] and ramp-sampling corrections, fundamental components of any modern EPI data acquisition.

Results:

Figure 1. Images reconstructed using custom Jupyter notebook (image on left produced by raw data from GE).

Sample images generated from the code and algorithms in the Jupyter notebook are displayed in figure 1. These images are comparable to those generated by the vendors’ default pipelines. Using the notebook, data have only undergone processing to handle data acquisition on the gradient ramps and Nyquist ghost corrections using the navigator reference data acquisitions integral to the imaging sequences, in addition to the requisite transforms needed to take the data from *k*- to image space. No other processing, such as *k*-space apodization or spatial normalization of intensity in image space, were performed on these data. Therefore, both vendors’ data were processed not only using identical algorithms, but with a single, common implementations of those algorithms – meaning that both vendors’ raw data received exactly equivalent treatment. Any necessary additional steps can be implemented by the user, and they would be independent of the vendors’ “black-box” implementation of these processes.

Discussion: Data acquired using the pulse sequences described above could be reconstructed using both each vendor’s default, built-in reconstruction pipelines, and the tools presented here. Proper labeling of data permitted the different EPI reference data encoding schemes from each vendor to be handled by relatively straightforward logic in the notebook. Handling that case is not as straight-forward in the Gadgetron [3], given tighter and more complex interdependencies of its components, which resulted in the higher ghosting levels in the Gadgetron-generated GE DICOM images in figure 2. DICOM images were generated from Siemens EPI data using a modified version of the “Generic_Cartesian_Grappa_EPI.xml” chain, while GE data were reconstructed using a custom configuration chain, “gtReconExampleGEEPI.xml.” Both of these reconstruction configurations are included in the same repository with the notebook.

By default, Siemens encodes timing information describing its ramp-sampled EPI acquisitions into its raw file format. GE instead provides a kernel which facilitates regridding ramp-sampled, non-uniformly spaced data, to uniformly spaced data (in *k*-space). Therefore, GE’s EPI pulse sequence was modified to embed corresponding timing information describing its ramp-sampled EPI acquisitions into its raw file format. When converted to ISMRMRD, this allowed usage of the same implemented algorithm, as was used for Siemens, to handle ramp-sampled data.

Figure 2. DICOMs reconstructed using Gadgetron (image on left produced by raw data from GE).

This work demonstrates that with adequate labeling of raw k -space data, tools can be developed to process and reconstruct such data from multiple vendors' platforms, even for complex data encodings and acquisition schemes previously only accessible through the vendors' proprietary, and usually closed-source, tools. Having a wide variety of tools, with varying levels of complexity, capabilities, and accessibility, can assist in the isolation and identification of errors, providing not only an ability to investigate more options and algorithms to address the issue, but also the ability to better focus efforts to solving problems. Tools with these types of capabilities will allow researchers to better characterize, control, and potentially reduce variance between scanners, both within and across vendors, sites, and harmonize data across studies.

References:

1. Uecker *et. al.* Berkeley Advanced Reconstruction Toolbox. Proc. ISMRM 2015, 2486.
2. Knopp and Grosser. MRIReco.jl: An Extensible Open-Source Image Reconstruction Framework written in Julia. Proc. ISMRM 2019, 4835.
3. Hansen and Sørensen. Gadgetron: An open source framework for medical image reconstruction. MRM, 69:6, 1768-1776, 2013.
4. Inati *et. al.* Gadgetron: ISMRM Raw data format: A proposed standard for MRI raw datasets. MRM, 77:1, 411-421, 2017.
5. Hu and Le. Artifact reduction in EPI with phase-encoded reference scan. MRM, 36:1, 166-171, 1996.

Resources: Link to publicly accessible forked repository of the GE to ISMRMRD converter code used in this work:

https://github.com/roopchansinghv/ge_to_ismrmrd/

Link for Jupyter notebook used:

https://github.com/roopchansinghv/ge_to_ismrmrd/blob/master/sampleData/notebooks/epiImportAndRecon.ipynb